

Analysis of trace metals in psilomelane manganese ore

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Convenient and accurate, direct current polarographic, differential pulse polarographic and differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetric methods have been developed for the simultaneous determination of metals at trace level in a psilomelane manganese ore sample. Statistical treatment of the observed voltammetric data reveals high accuracy and good precision of determination. The observed voltammetric results are compared with those obtained using atomic absorption spectroscopic method.

Psilomelane, ore of manganese, is generally associated with Fe, which constitutes major part of the sample¹. However, some other metal ions, such as Cd, Pb, Al, Ni, Co, Cr, V, Mg, etc. are also present in it in trace amounts². A survey of literature reveals that trace analysis of manganese ore samples has been carried out mainly by using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and atomic absorption spectrometric (AAS) methods³. Besides, there are many other analytical methods for the trace metal analysis in natural origin samples⁴. Polarographic and voltammetric methods have also been used for such an analyses⁵. The usefulness of electroanalytical techniques, viz. DCP, DPP and DPASV is well established⁶. Looking at the advantageous features of electroanalytical techniques, we have undertaken the analysis of psilomelane manganese ore for its trace metals content, the results of which are described here.

Results and Discussion

The nature of the supporting electrolyte plays a significant role in polarographic/voltammetric analysis. After detailed study it was found that 0.1 M (NH₄)-tartrate is an ideal medium for trace metals determination in manganese ore. The direct current polarogram and differential pulse polarogram [Fig. 1(A)] of the sample solution in 0.1 M (NH₄)-tartrate (pH = 9.0 ± 0.1) produced three distinct waves/peaks with $E_{1/2}/E_p = -0.50/-0.54$ V, $-0.68/-0.07$ V and $-1.10/-1.12$ V vs SCE, indicating the presence of Tl^I, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}, respectively. In addition, one more wave/peak was observed with $E_{1/2}/E_p = -1.66/-1.68$ V vs SCE, indicating the presence of some other metal ions in the sample, which was confirmed by changing the pH of the test solution to 9.7 ± 0.1. At this pH, the wave/peak splitted into two [Fig. 1(C)] with $E_{1/2}/E_p = -1.56/-56$ V and $-1.64/-1.67$ V vs SCE, corresponding to the presence of Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} metals ions, respectively.

The differential pulse anodic stripping voltammograms

Fig. 1. (A) Differential pulse polarogram of psilomelane manganese ore sample in 0.1 M ammonium tartrate + 0.001% gelatin, pH = 9.0 ± 0.1. (B) Differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of psilomelane manganese ore sample in 0.1 M ammonium tartrate + 0.001% gelatin, pH = 9.0 ± 0.1. (C) Differential pulse polarogram of psilomelane manganese ore sample in 0.1 M ammonium tartrate + 0.001% gelatin, pH = 9.7 ± 0.1. (D) Differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of psilomelane manganese ore sample in 0.1 M ammonium tartrate + 0.001% gelatin, pH = 9.7 ± 0.1.

Table 1. Results on psilomelane manganese ore sample analysis for metal ions (mg g⁻¹)*

Metal ions	Parameter	DCP		DPP		DPASV		AAS
		Added	Found	Added	Found	Added	Found	
Tl ^I	Amount	–	25.80	–	25.80	–	25.80	25.75
		25.55	51.30	25.55	51.28	25.55	51.32	
	R%		99.9%		99.8%		99.9%	
	S.D.		0.02		0.02		0.09	
Cd ^{II}	Amount	–	3.74	–	3.74	–	3.74	3.76
		3.37	7.06	3.37	7.06	3.37	7.08	
	R%		99.3%		99.3%		99.6%	
	S.D.		0.02		0.04		0.02	
Ni ^{II}	Amount	–	2.75	–	2.76	–	2.75	2.71
		2.34	4.98	2.34	5.02	2.34	5.06	
	R%		98.0%		98.4%		99.4%	
	S.D.		0.04		0.008		0.02	
Fe ^{II}	Amount	–	38.68	–	38.68	–	38.68	38.67
		39.06	77.69	39.06	77.64	39.06	77.52	
	R%		99.9%		99.8%		99.7%	
	S.D.		0.05		0.05		0.05	
Mn ^{II}	Amount	–	283.65	–	283.65	–	283.66	283.59
		274.5	565.80	274.5	556.80	274.5	557.05	
	R%		99.7%		99.7%		99.8%	
	S.D.		0.03		0.02		0.02	
		0.01%		0.007%		0.008%		

*Results are average of four determination; R% = recovery (%), S.D. = standard deviation, C.V. = coefficient of variation.

[Fig. 1(B) and (D)] of the sample in 0.1 M (NH₄)-tartrate at both pHs 9.0 ± 0.1 and 9.7 ± 0.1 were recorded using glassy carbon fibre electrode. The voltammograms showed three well-defined peaks at pH 9.0 ± 0.1 with E_p values of –0.52, –0.76 and –1.04 V vs SCE, and at pH 9.7 ± 0.1, the voltammogram showed two peaks with E_p = –1.46 and –1.56 V vs SCE, indicating the presence of Tl^I, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III} and Mn^{II}, respectively.

To ascertain, the presence of the said metal ions in the sample, a known quantity of standard solution of each metal ion was added to the analyte and polarograms and voltammograms were recorded under the identical experimental conditions. An increase in the wave/peak height of ion signal was observed without any change in its $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values.

After confirming the presence of the above mentioned metal ions, some synthetic samples of varying concentrations of the said metal ions were prepared and their polarograms and voltammograms were recorded under identical experimental conditions. The signals resulted in the increase of each wave/peak height without any change in $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values of the above mentioned metal ions, thus confirming the possibility of an accurate simultaneous multielement qualitative and quantitative determination of the said metal ions in the sample. The concentration of each metal ion was determined in synthetic samples using DPP method.

The minimum tried detection limits of the DCP, DPP and DPASV techniques, for the measurement of individual and combined metal ions were examined by preparing synthetic samples. Of these Tl^I, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} were determined in one run at pH 9.0 ± 0.1, and other metal ions, viz. Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} were determined at pH 9.7 ± 0.1. The data show that the DPASV method using glassy carbon fibre electrode is highly sensitive in determining the metal ions down to nanogram level.

After ascertaining the presence of the said metal ions in the sample, the quantitative analysis of metals in the sample was carried out using the method of standard addition. The results (Table 1) reveal that the recovery is over 99% for most of the metal ions, with high accuracy and precision of determination.

These voltammetric results were compared with those obtained on the psilomelane manganese ore sample using atomic absorption spectroscopic method. The agreement between the two data demonstrates the utility of voltammetric methods for such an analyses.

Experimental

The psilomelane manganese ore sample collected from Bharveli Mine, District Balaghat, M.P. (India) was procured from the Department of Applied Geology, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, India.

Polarographic and voltammetric measurements were made on an Elico CL-90 polarograph. The electrode system

consisted of a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as a working electrode, a coiled platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode. The electrochemical cell used had the provision for inserting a bubbler for deaerating the solution. A glassy carbon fibre electrode (NF 12, Sigitii Eletitiogitit, U.K.) was used for stripping voltammetric analysis. pH was measured on a Systronics 335 pH-meter.

The instrumental parameters for polarographic and voltammetric analysis were fixed as follows : pulse amplitude, 50 mV; drop time, 0.5 s; I.R. compensation, 4; C.C. compensation, 5; time constant, 10 ms; sensitivity, 1 $\mu\text{A/V}$; scan rate, 12 mV s^{-1} . For DPASV the deposition potential was fixed at -2.0 V , deposition time 60 s and resting period 10 s. All experiments were performed at $25 \pm 2^\circ$.

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Stock solutions of ammonium tartrate (1 M), Tl^{I} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} (0.01 M) were prepared by dissolving the required amounts of their soluble salts in double-distilled water. The solutions were standardized by known methods and diluted as required. Gelatin (0.1%) solution was prepared in hot distilled water.

Preparation of sample solution : Finely pulverized psilomelane manganese ore sample (1.0 g) was heated with conc. HCl (50 ml), then filtered. The undissolved white residue was dissolved by heating it with conc. HF (5 ml). Both the solutions were mixed and the final volume was made to 100 ml with double-distilled water.

Preparation of analyte and recording of voltammograms : To the sample solution (10 ml), were added 1 M $(\text{NH}_4)\text{-tartrate}$ (10 ml) and of 0.1% gelatin (1 ml) as maximum suppressor, and the final volume was made up to 100 ml with double-distilled water. Its pH was first adjusted to

9.0 ± 0.1 and then to 9.7 ± 0.1 with NH_4OH solution, as the analysis of the sample solution was carried out at two different pH values. The analyte was placed in a polarographic cell equipped with the electrode assembly specified above. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for 15 min at the beginning of experiment. Then the polarograms and voltammograms were recorded.

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